

Message of Sri Ramakrishna and Revisiting Indian Society

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Abstract:

Indian society is undergoing a growing crisis related to a much debated issue ‘Indianness’ – a sentiment of being an Indian – socially, culturally and spiritually. This logocentric term ‘Indianness’ implies a monolithic characteristic of Indian people. Thought, action, behaviour, movement – all are under the lens of (in)visible eyes to shape all the Indians in a same mould. Democracy itself appears as a socio-political normativism as if it ought to be upheld by everyone. Plurality of reasons is being limited because of such normativity. At this time, message of Sri Ramakrishna, a well-known but ‘non-intellectual’ Bangalee legend, might be thought provoking while ‘Indianness’ lacks plurality of reasons. Once Sri Ramakrishna said ‘*jato mat tato path*’. He taught mankind to believe in all-inclusiveness irrespective of people’s social, cultural and spiritual identity. His thought supports plurality of reasons and subjective reality which are the need of the hour in present day Indian context. This paper, therefore, intends to highlight the relevance of the message of Sri Ramakrishna in present day India.

Keywords: Sri Ramakrishna, Indianness, normativism, plurality of reasons, subjective reality.

Introduction:

It might be worthwhile to start with the term ‘Indianness’. The term ‘Indianness’ denotes a sentiment of being an Indian – socially, culturally and spiritually. More elaborately it can be said that Indianness implies that every Indian has to be complied with the sentiment of Indian nation not merely geographically or physically but socially, culturally and spiritually. In this context, to be an Indian means to be consciously or unconsciously devoted to the soul and mind of India. But, now, the most significant question seems to be what standard is to be achieved as to be devoted with the soul and mind of the nation? Which social characteristics, cultural context and religious belief are to be taken complementary with ‘Indianness’? Is there any exercise of power to set the values to be an Indian, or has ‘Indianness’ been dogmatized by those who possess power?

Modern age is the age of normativism. Normativism is always set up by the dominant outlook of the society and a production of power relations. Normativism means primacy or desirability of such social norms which *ought to be* maintained by the people. The question of Indianness might be examined by the theory of normativism. ‘Indianness’, is being patronized by some social, cultural and spiritual ideologies, produces power relations between the ‘dominant’ and the ‘other’. Thought, action, behaviour, movement – all are under the lens of (in)visible eyes to shape all the Indians in a same mould¹. Thus, Indianness produces intolerance in society as it is, now, enclaved by a monolithic socio-cultural-religious identity². It can be said the Indianness is a logocentric term because it is a fundamental

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expression of an external reality which ignores the internal differences of meaning within the term.³ Therefore, Indian society is gradually lacking plurality since what should be the criteria to be a true Indian is being determined by the pre-hypothesized characteristics of Indianness.

Sri Ramakrishna and Revisiting Indian Society:

In this context, the messages of Sri Ramakrishna, a well-known but ‘non-intellectual’ Bangalee legend, might be thought provoking while Indian society lacks plurality of reasons. The name Sri Ramakrishna is self-explanatory because of his journey from Gadadhar Chattopadhyay to Sri Ramakrishna. His spiritual presence is beyond explanation by the theories of politics or sociology and he is not confined to the past, present and future epoch⁴, but his messages are perpetual in any time and space. Here, Sri Ramakrishna is invoked due to his everlasting thoughts about human being. Sri Ramakrishna took the people subjectively rather than objectively. Once he said ‘*manush ki kam ga?*’ (Do you know how immense potential does a human being have?). Then people is important to him irrespective of people’s social, cultural and spiritual identity.

Now, Indian society might be examined by three theoretical contexts – exclusivism, inclusivism and pluralism. Indian society is traditionally multicultural, multilingual, and multi-religious. Exclusivism promotes this inner division of society by depriving ‘others’, while inclusivism tries to provide a shelter to the differences through assimilating all under one umbrella. Whereas pluralism recognizes the differences by allowing all equally, sidestepping all the normativity. Sri Ramakrishna believed in pluralism and empathy because, to him, salvation existences in every religion and no religion is superior or normative over the rest to offer a path to the divine reality. Every individual, every culture or every group must be seen from their point of view. He said ‘*jato mat tato path*’ (as many faiths, so many ways). His very message of ‘*jato mat tato path*’ is definitely based on the subjective reality which is, after more or less one century, popularized by the postmodernists.⁵ One example might be interesting here to understand how Sri Ramakrishna could discard orthodoxy of the religion. At that time Sri Ramakrishna was counting his last days in Cossipore and his disciples Naren (Swami Vivekananda), Sarat and Kali were not there for a considerable time.

After seeing Sarat he asked, where had you gone?

Sarat: to Piru’s hotel at Barahanagar.

Sri Ramakrishna: why?

Sarat: Naren invited to have forbidden bird’s (chicken) meat and Mughlai paratha.

Sri Ramakrishna: have you eaten?

Sarat: no, as soon as I saw it, I vomited.

Sri Ramakrishna: has Kali eaten?

Sarat: as soon as he tasted it, he vomited.

Sri Ramakrishna: and Naren?

Sarat: yes, not only his share but our shares too.

Sri Ramakrishna: That fellow has done the right thing. A Sannyasin does not discriminate!⁶

This conversation is very much relevant in present day India while food habit of people is being questioned from a normative outlook. What Sri Ramakrishna could think more than a century back, most of the Indians, irrespective of communities, cannot think even at present day. Sri Ramakrishna was very much intimate to many people from *Brahmo Samaj*. Mahendranath Gupta wrote:

Many followers of *Brahmo Samaj* often came to meet *Thakur*. Keshab, Vijay, Kali (Basu), Pratap, Shivanath, Amrit, Trailokya, Krishna Bihari, Manilal, Umesh, Hirananda, Bhavani, Nanda Lal and many other *Brahmo bhaktas* often visited him.

Thakur would also go to meet the *Brahmos*. During the lifetime of Mathur, *Thakur* went with him to Debendranath Tagore's house and paid a visit to the *Adi Brahma Samaj* during the service hours. Later on, he went to see Keshab's *Brahmo* temple and *Sadharan Samaj* during the worship time. He would frequently visit Keshab's house. How immensely did he enjoy the company of *Brahmo bhaktas*! Keshab also visited him frequently sometimes with *bhaktas*, sometimes alone.⁷

Sri Ramakrishna never took the religion as it can divide people due to their religious beliefs. Rather, for Sri Ramakrishna, humanism is the best way to realize the God. One conversation between Ramakrishna and Mahendranath Gupta (Master) on Keshab Chandra Sen might be relevant here:

Sri Ramakrishna: Well, how is Keshab doing at present? He was seriously ill.

Master: I too have heard the same, perhaps he is well now.

Sri Ramakrishna: I made a vow to offer a green coconut and sugar to the Divine Mother (Goddess Kali) for Keshab's recovery. I would sometimes wake up at midnight and cry before the Mother, saying, 'O Mother, may Keshab get well. If Keshab does not live, whom shall I talk to when I go to Calcutta?' That is why I vowed to offer green coconut and sugar.⁸

This conversation is relevant because Keshab Chandra Sen was a follower of *Brahmo Samaj*, and relation between Hinduism and *Brahmo* religion was undergoing a tension due to their different religious philosophy. But Sri Ramakrishna tried to harmonize the religious beliefs irrespective of the differences among religions. Mahendranath Gupta wrote:

To realize the harmony of all religions, *Thakur*, on the one hand, practised the disciplines of the Vaishnavas, the Shaktas, the Shaivites, and so on. On the other hand, he recited the name of Allah and meditated upon Christ. In the room where he lived, there were pictures of gods and an image of the Buddha. There was also a picture showing Jesus Christ saving Peter from drowning in the water. These pictures can still be seen if you enter that room.⁹

One statement of Sri Ramakrishna is relevant here: 'he who can achieve harmony, is unique for me, I find all human beings, whatever religion they practised, are equal'¹⁰. Religion cannot divide people because every religion has to take the good principles from other religions. Swami Ghanananda speaks about the 'sevenfold harmony' as it can be found from the message of Sri Ramakrishna¹¹: 1. among different religions, 2. among different Philosophical sects, 3. Among various paths of spirituality, 4. Between God and *Brahmo*, 5. among various spiritual realizations, 6. among various communities within a religion, and 7. among various *varnas*. Here, the message of Sri Ramakrishna might be linked to the recently much cherished concept of 'social capital'¹². Social capital can be described as goodwill, fellowship, sympathy, trust, norms, and networks among the people of a society. In other words, social capital means a strong and ceaseless reciprocal relations among the people in a society based on some social norms and ethics. It connects people across diverse social groups – bridging social capital; and brings people together from homogenous groups – bonding social capital.

This is the instance of plurality of reasons upheld by Sri Ramakrishna, who was not so-called formally educated or he had not learnt 'secularism'. He tried to uphold plurality of reasons in his own way. Indian society is gradually lacking pluralism. Even democracy is failed to promote plurality in Indian society. Democracy itself appears as a socio-political normativism as if it ought to be upheld by everyone. Democracy hardly speaks for all, but for the dominant section.

Concluding Remarks:

If individuality and free thinking are the inherent characteristics of renaissance, then Sri Ramakrishna first initiated renaissance in Indian religious domain. Simplification in religious practices instead of performative religious rituals guided by the grand narrative holy books, was initiated by Sri Ramakrishna. He tried to weed out the caste system and untouchability. There is no room for casteism, rituals and religious formalities in his religion. Scriptural rules are not infallible or unchangeable in his opinion. According to him, to serve the human being is the true religion. That is humanism.¹³ Based on Sri Ramakrishna's message '*jatro jeeb tatro Shib*' (in every being resides the God), Swami Vivekananda had preached '*jeebe prem kore jei jon, sei jon sebiche Ishwar*' (who loves all beings without distinction, he indeed is worshipping best his God). This was the foremost philosophy behind the establishment of the Ramakrishna Mission by Swami Vivekananda. The primary aim of the Ramakrishna Mission is *seva* (service to the mankind) not based on kindness but empathy. Swami Vivekananda once said Sri Ramakrishna is ever-eternal proposer of all the religious thoughts exist not only in India, but in the world.¹⁴ Sri Ramakrishna tried to reconcile the dichotomies between monism (*advaitabad*) and dualism (*dvaitabad*); between *sākārabāda* and *nirākārabāda*. Rabindranath Tagore offered tribute to him as:

‘Diverse courses of worship
From varied springs of fulfilment
Have mingled in your meditation.
The manifold revelation of the joy of the infinite
Has given form to a Shrine of Unity in your life.’¹⁵

Sri Ramakrishna never separated himself from the human society like other saints. He was deeply embedded within the society that is why the universal relevance of Sri Ramakrishna never be ignored.¹⁶ Then the message of Sri Ramakrishna is still relevant while intolerance is often seen due to the question of Indianness. So, it can be said, borrowed from Sri Ramakrishna, '*tomader chaitanya hok*' (may your consciousness manifest).

¹ Here, I want to mean the presence of surveillance everywhere in society, being inspired by the Foucauldian notion of disciplinary power. People are under surveillance of many judges in society. Foucault said, in his *Discipline and Punish* (1975), that 'the judges of normality are present everywhere. We are in the society of the teacher-judge, the doctor-judge, the educator-judge, the 'social worker'-judge; it is on them that the universal reign of the normative is based; and each individual, wherever he may find himself, subjects to it his body, his gestures, his behaviour, his aptitudes, his achievements.'

² Many examples of intolerance can be given here. For instance, food habit of people is now questioned by the dominant section due to it is not compatible to the 'Indian culture'. Recently, Indianness of Virat Kohli and Anushka Sharma has also been questioned as they got married in Italy instead of any place of India.

³ Here, I used the concept of Derrida. In *Of Grammatology* (1967), Derrida formulated this concept which proposes that language originates as a process of thought which produces speech, and that speech produces writing. Logocentrism inspires us to treat linguistic signs as distinct from and inessential to the phenomena they represent. Logocentrism, according to Derrida, is a 'metaphysics of presence', which is motivated by a desire for a 'transcendental signified'. For example, Indianness does not represent the differences within the word itself, but, being used by 'self-acclaimed' upholders of Indianness, reflects a transcendental meaning of it.

⁴ Recently, this area has been focused in *Desh*. See Ahmed, Shamim, "Sri Ramakrishna Paramhamsadeber Sarbadharmo Samonway," *Desh*, 2 January 2018, p. 30.

⁵ Here, I tried to relate the idea of Sri Ramakrishna with postmodernism. Jean-Francois Lyotard, in his *The Postmodern Condition: A Report on Knowledge* (1979), defined postmodernism as ‘incredulity toward metanarratives’. I think ‘*jato mot tato path*’ is also incredulity towards a monolithic way of thinking or to achieve one’s goal. Here, I never substantiated Sri Ramakrishna by postmodernism, but tried to show that Sri Ramakrishna taught us hundred years back of what Lyotard proposed.

⁶ Ahmed, Shamim, op. cit. p. 29 (Translated from Bengali)

⁷ *Sri Sri Ramakrishna Kathamrita*, Kolkata: Udbodhan Karyalaya, 2015. p. 6 (translated from Bengali).

⁸ Ibid. p. 16 (translated from Bengali).

⁹ Ibid. p. 6 (translated from Bengali).

¹⁰ Translated, but not word to word. See Dhar, Sachchidananda. "Sri Ramakrishna: Samonway – Byakti O Biswa Jibane." *Biswa Chetanai Sri Ramakrishna*. Ed. Swami Prameyananda, Nalini Ranjan Chattopadhyay and Swami Chaitnyananda. Kolkata: Udbodhan, 1987. p. 319.

¹¹ Ghanananda, Swami, *Sri Ramakrishna and His Unique Message*, 3rd. London: Ramakrishna Vedanta Centre, 1970. pp. 116-33.

¹² The concept of social capital has been developed by the work of Pierre Bourdieu (1986), James C. Coleman (1988) and it is further developed by Robert Putnam in his seminal work ‘*Bowling Alone*’ (2000).

¹³ See Mukhopadhyay, Jiban, "Sri Ramakrishna O Bharatiyo Nabajagoran", in *Biswa Chetanai Sri Ramakrishna*. Ed. Swami Prameyananda, Nalini Ranjan Chattopadhyay and Swami Chaitnyananda. Kolkata: Udbodhan, 1987. p. 154.

¹⁴ Ibid. p. 157.

¹⁵ This poem, written by Rabindranath Tagore, was published first in Udbodhan in its Sri Ramakrishna birth-centenary year issue, 1936. I have taken this English translation from Arun Kumar Biswas. See Biswas, Arun Kumar, “Syncretism and the Future of Humankind: Some Golden Thoughts of Vivekananda”, in *Vivekananda as the Turning Point: The Rise of a New Spiritual Wave*, ed. Swami Shuddhidananda, Kolkata: Advaita Ashrama, 2013. p. 260.

¹⁶ This area has recently been focused by Martin Kämpchen. For details, see Kämpchen, Martin, “Sri Ramakrishner Biswajanin Tatporjo”, *Desh*, 2 January 2018. p. 22.